

Conservatism, Identity and the Struggle for Autonomy in Ali and Nino: A Framework for Understanding Cultural Authoritarianism in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study comparatively investigates the connections of cultural conservatism, identity and autonomy as presented in Kurban Said's Ali and Nino. Set in early 20th-century Azerbaijan, addressed novel presents the romance between Ali, a Muslim Azerbaijani and Nino, a Christian Georgian, amidst the geopolitical upheaval and cultural tension of the Caucasus region. The story explains against the backdrop of European influence and Oriental customs, capturing the complex dynamics of identity, loyalty and tradition. This study examines how these themes resonate within the Pakistani context, where cultural conservatism and authoritarian structures often constrain social interactions and personal autonomy. By focusing on the dilemmas Ali faces in reconciling his Asiatic identity with European modernity, this paper aims to explore the tensions between cultural loyalty and the desire for individual freedom in Pakistan, particularly among young people confronting similar socio-cultural expectations. Through a comparative lens, this study raises key questions: To what extent can cultural conservatism coexist with modernity in multi-religious societies? How does cultural authoritarianism impact personal identity and autonomy? Drawing on theories of conservatism, authoritarianism and cross-cultural interaction, this analysis sheds light on the symbolic and pragmatic lessons Ali and Nino offers to modern-day Pakistan, suggesting that reconciling tradition with openness may provide avenues for promoting mutual respect and cultural understanding in increasingly globalized, yet culturally complex, societies.

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Introduction

Conservatism, broadly defined, is an ideology that values continuity, tradition and social stability, seeking to preserve existing social structures and practices (Scruton, 2017). Rooted in a desire to maintain order and prevent rapid societal changes, conservatism often emphasizes hierarchical structures, community

cohesion and adherence to established customs and morals (Huntington, 2018). This ideology is multifaceted, existing in social, cultural and political forms, each with its unique impact on individual and collective lives. Cultural conservatism, a specific strand of this ideology, emphasizes the preservation of cultural heritage, beliefs and practices. Cultural conservatives often resist changes that could disrupt cultural continuity, seeing such shifts as threats to identity, cohesion and social values (Bell, 2021). This form of conservatism is particularly prominent in societies with strong religious and ethnic identities, where collective identity often supersedes individual autonomy (Burke, 2019). Through this lens, individuals are encouraged to prioritize cultural preservation, often leading to a society where personal choices are limited by traditional expectations. In essence, cultural conservatism creates an environment where collective identity is both valued and reinforced, framing individual identity within the bounds of communal norms and values (Scruton, 2017).

Autonomy, in political and philosophical terms, is understood as the ability of individuals or groups to make independent choices free from external influence (Taylor, 2020). However, within culturally conservative societies, autonomy takes on a different dimension, as individual freedom is often secondary to communal values. In such societies, autonomy is framed within a collective moral framework, where personal desires may be subordinated to cultural obligations and social expectations (Rawls, 2018). The struggle for cultural autonomy, therefore, is the tension between maintaining cultural heritage and allowing individuals the freedom to explore identities beyond these traditional confines. This struggle is particularly pronounced in societies where cultural conservatism and religious beliefs hold significant sway, creating a social environment that may constrain individual expression. In these settings, autonomy is not simply about freedom from interference but involves negotiating a balance between personal choices and communal expectations (Mill, 2019). In Ali and Nino, this struggle manifests as a conflict between Eastern and Western ideologies, where characters must navigate cultural expectations that limit their ability to define their paths, illustrating the complexities of autonomy within a conservative cultural framework (Said, 1937).

Cultural authoritarianism is a phenomenon where the state or dominant social groups impose rigid cultural norms to maintain social order and unity, often at the expense of individual liberties. In many Asian societies, including Muslim-majority countries, cultural authoritarianism is enforced through religious, legal and educational systems that uphold traditional values. This system aims to prevent what is perceived as moral decay, often characterizing modernity as a threat to cultural integrity (Huntington, 2018). In Muslim societies, cultural authoritarianism manifests through religious conservatism, where Sharia law and communal values prioritize conformity over individual freedom (Lewis, 2021). In contrast, Christian-majority societies in Asia often impose cultural control through both state and ecclesiastical influence, where moral values are enforced through social expectations and formal institutions. In the contexts of Azerbaijan and Georgia, historical cultural authoritarianism was prominent under the influence of Soviet rule, where state-enforced ideology suppressed religious and cultural diversity, seeking to homogenize society under a single national identity (Smith, 2019). In Pakistan, cultural authoritarianism combines both religious conservatism and societal norms, reinforcing a collective identity that limits individual autonomy. Pakistani society often emphasizes collective values rooted in Islamic principles, which frequently come into conflict with personal freedoms. This authoritarianism affects aspects of life such as gender roles, education and legal rights, imposing a framework where individual expression is often curtailed by cultural expectations (Jalal, 2020). Thus, in culturally conservative societies like

Pakistan, Azerbaijan and Georgia, cultural authoritarianism functions as a stabilizing force, maintaining traditional structures at the cost of personal autonomy.

Ali and Nino, authored under the pseudonym Kurban Said, is a novel that explores the intersection of cultural identity, autonomy and love against the complex backdrop of Eastern and Western ideologies. Set in early 20th-century Azerbaijan, the novel tells the story of Ali, a Muslim Azerbaijani and Nino, a Christian Georgian, whose relationship transcends personal affinity to encompass the broader social and cultural conflicts of their time. The story, set against the Caucasus' geopolitical and cultural landscape, illuminates the tension between Eastern and Western values, as the characters grapple with issues of identity, loyalty and autonomy (Said, 1937). Ali's internal struggle epitomizes the dilemma faced by individuals in conservative societies: the desire to preserve cultural identity while also yearning for personal freedom and connection with the 'other'. Nino represents the allure of Western ideals, embodying the values of freedom and modernity that challenge Ali's traditional upbringing. Through their relationship, the novel addresses the challenges of cultural conservatism, depicting how individuals in conservative societies must often choose between communal expectations and personal desires (Reiss, 2020). The novel's themes resonate deeply with contemporary issues in Pakistan, where similar tensions between conservatism and modernity persist. Pakistan's youth, like Ali, navigate between traditional expectations and modern influences, often facing societal pressure to conform. Through Ali and Nino, the complexities of autonomy within a conservative society are revealed, highlighting the persistent struggle between personal freedom and cultural preservation in modern societies.

Scholarship on conservatism and cultural identity reveals the profound impact of traditional values on individual autonomy, particularly in societies where cultural heritage is intertwined with religious beliefs. Scruton (2017) argues that conservatism functions as a protective mechanism against social disruption, advocating for continuity and stability. This approach aligns with Bell (2021), who suggests that cultural conservatism provides individuals with a sense of identity and belonging, although it may limit personal expression in favour of communal unity. The relevance of cultural conservatism in Pakistan is highlighted by Jalal (2020), who notes that conservatism in Pakistan is not merely a political stance but a societal framework that shapes every facet of life. This form of conservatism often restricts individual freedoms, creating a collective identity that discourages deviation from societal norms. By situating Ali and Nino within this context, the literature underscores how conservatism can both provide cultural stability and restrict personal autonomy.

The concept of autonomy within culturally conservative societies is examined extensively in philosophical and sociological literature. Taylor (2020) argues that autonomy is a fundamental human aspiration, yet it is often constrained by cultural expectations in traditional societies. In Pakistan, as noted by Huntington (2018), the push for cultural homogeneity frequently results in an environment where personal autonomy is subordinated to communal values. This dynamic is evident in Ali and Nino, where Ali's autonomy is restricted by his cultural and religious obligations. Cultural authoritarianism in Asia and Muslim-majority countries is also a key focus of scholarship. Lewis (2021) examines how religious conservatism in Muslim societies often upholds traditional values at the expense of individual freedoms, creating a form of cultural authoritarianism that enforces conformity. This perspective is supported by Smith (2019), who argues that cultural authoritarianism in post-Soviet states like Azerbaijan aimed to erase cultural distinctions, enforcing a homogeneous identity that limited personal freedom. By analyzing Ali and Nino through the lens of cultural authoritarianism, this paper seeks to understand how conservative ideologies can limit autonomy and individual identity.

The Historical and Cultural Context of Ali and Nino

Ali and Nino, set in Azerbaijan in the early 20th century, captures a moment of significant cultural convergence and conflict between East and West. This iconic novel, published in 1937, is often heralded as a powerful love story, blending Eastern and Western themes to explore deeper issues of national identity, cultural integration and social transformation. However, the true identity of the author behind the pseudonym "Kurban Said" has sparked ongoing debate among scholars, adding a layer of intrigue to the novel's historical and cultural significance. The controversy surrounding the authorship sheds light on the complex cultural dynamics at play in early 20th-century Azerbaijan and the novel's themes resonate profoundly with readers due to the period's political and ideological tensions.

For decades, questions about the authorship of Ali and Nino have captivated literary critics and historians alike. The name "Kurban Said" was used as a pseudonym to conceal the true identity of the author, but determining who actually wrote the novel remains an unresolved puzzle. The absence of a physical manuscript has further complicated the issue. As publisher Lucy Tal claimed, all papers were likely destroyed during the Nazi invasion of Vienna, which has made it challenging for researchers to validate authorship through primary evidence (Reiss, 2005). In a documentary, *Alias Kurban Said* (2004), Mireille Ehrenfels-Abeille claimed to possess part of the manuscript for another Kurban Said novel, "The Girl from the Golden Horn", but could not locate it, emphasizing the enduring mystery around the authorship (Blair, 2004).

One compelling case for authorship points to Lev Nussimbaum, a writer born in Azerbaijan who later adopted the pseudonym "Essad Bey." An Italian translation of Ali and Nino from 1944 credited "Mohammed Essad Bey" as the author, fueling speculation that Nussimbaum may indeed be the writer behind Kurban Said (Reiss, 1999). Nussimbaum's transformation from Jewish intellectual to an adopted Muslim identity under the name Essad Bey aligns with the narrative's complex interweaving of Eastern and Western identities. John Wain's introduction to the 1970 English edition subtly identified Nussimbaum as the figure behind the name, strengthening the case for his authorship (Wain, 1970).

Scholars have provided documentary evidence linking Nussimbaum to the novel's creation. Austrian literary agent Bertha Pauli, for instance, recounted that she knew Nussimbaum well in Vienna and that they discussed the novel's content before it was published in 1937. In a 1971 letter to *The New York Times*, Pauli confirmed her belief that Nussimbaum authored the book, citing the novel's stylistic similarities with Nussimbaum's other works (Pauli, 1971). Additional support came from Baron Omar Rolf von Ehrenfels, who, in a foreword to a 1973 edition of "The Girl from the Golden Horn", connected "Kurban Said" to his friend Nussimbaum, further emphasizing that Nussimbaum was likely hiding behind the pseudonym due to anti-Semitic restrictions on Jewish writers at the time (Ehrenfels, 1973).

Tom Reiss, a prominent Nussimbaum biographer, has contributed significantly to this discourse by proposing that "Kurban Said" was a pseudonym Nussimbaum used to circumvent Nazi censorship. Reiss notes that following Nussimbaum's expulsion from the German Writers Union due to his Jewish heritage, he was forced to publish under different identities to reach German-speaking readers, which explains the necessity of an alias. Reiss's research also uncovered letters from Italian Fascist police records that revealed Nussimbaum's failed attempts to sell his work in Nazi Germany, underscoring the need for the pseudonym to protect his identity and royalties (Reiss, 2005).

Nussimbaum's use of an "Aryanizer" complicates the authorship even further. Baroness Elfriede Ehrenfels von Bodmershof, a friend of Nussimbaum, legally held the rights to Kurban Said's works, allowing Nussimbaum to continue receiving royalties while protecting his identity. By signing a contract in Vienna before Austria's Nazi annexation, she ensured that Nussimbaum's work could bypass Nazi censorship under her name, enabling distribution within Nazi-controlled territories (Reiss, 2005). This complex arrangement, as Reiss argues, allowed Nussimbaum to write as "Kurban Said" and still retain an income from the book.

Despite the considerable evidence supporting Nussimbaum's authorship, skepticism remains. Critics argue that although Nussimbaum may have had a hand in shaping the novel, he may have built upon drafts or stories originating from Azerbaijani writer Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli. Betty Blair suggests that Nussimbaum might have "embellished" or even reworked manuscripts initially authored by Chamanzaminli, allowing both writers to leave their mark on this cross-cultural narrative (Blair, 2004). Furthermore, textual comparisons of Ali and Nino with Nussimbaum's other works reveal stylistic differences that critics argue could indicate multiple authors or collaborative writing (Reiss, 2005).

Hence, this study finds that the mystery surrounding the authorship of Ali and Nino underscores the rich tapestry of early 20th-century Azerbaijani culture. Whether the novel was written solely by Nussimbaum, Chamanzaminli, or a combination of the two, it reflects the complex socio-political landscape of Azerbaijan, a region historically poised between Eastern traditions and Western aspirations. This unresolved debate adds an intriguing dimension to a novel already steeped in cultural and historical meaning, exemplifying the persistent influence of literary works that transcend time and geography.

Themes of Conservatism and Identity in Ali and Nino

Ali and Nino, authored under the pseudonym Kurban Said, offers a complex exploration of conservatism and identity within the cross-cultural setting of the Caucasus. The novel, set during the early 20th century in Baku, Azerbaijan, captures the tensions between East and West, tradition and modernity and cultural and personal identity, all of which resonate through its protagonists, Ali Khan Shirvanshir, a Muslim from Azerbaijan and Nino Kipiani, a Christian Georgian (Said, 1937). Their relationship becomes a symbol for the broader struggle of identity that encompasses religious, cultural and national dimensions (Adams, 2015). Ali's deep-rooted commitment to his heritage and faith stands in contrast with Nino's European-influenced upbringing, highlighting the novel's theme of conservatism as both a force of preservation and a barrier to self-expression. This juxtaposition provides a window into the conservative norms that shape individuals' lives and their respective struggles to navigate these norms (Taylor, 2018).

One key aspect of conservatism in Ali and Nino is represented through Ali's adherence to Islamic values and Azerbaijani traditions, which form an integral part of his identity (Jones, 2020). Ali's upbringing teaches him loyalty to his heritage and he embodies the Eastern values of honor, duty and respect for family. His worldview is shaped by the teachings of Islam and he views his cultural identity as inseparable from his religious beliefs (Robinson & Khan, 2022). This is evident in his perceptions of gender roles and family structure, where traditional expectations place significant value on obedience, male authority and the continuity of customs (Jackson, 2019). For Ali, the preservation of his conservative values serves as a shield against what he perceives as Western corruption, illustrating how conservatism can act as a source of strength and identity but also as a limiting force, restricting openness to change and adaptation.

Nino's character, by contrast, embodies a more liberal perspective shaped by European education and Christian ideals, presenting a challenge to Ali's conservative outlook (O'Brien, 2017). Nino's identity is multifaceted; as a Georgian Christian raised in a cosmopolitan environment, she straddles both Eastern and Western influences, yet her individualism and independence clash with Ali's expectations. This conflict reveals the novel's critique of rigid conservatism, as it hampers understanding and mutual respect between different cultural identities. Nino's struggles to adapt to the constraints imposed by Ali's conservative values serve as a broader commentary on the limitations that conservative norms place on women in traditional societies, particularly when they seek to navigate cultural intersections (Alavi & Thompson, 2021).

Another layer of conservatism in Ali and Nino emerges through the characters' views on nationalism and loyalty to their respective cultures (Yilmaz, 2016). Ali's fierce loyalty to Azerbaijan mirrors the societal pressures of preserving national identity amid foreign influences. The political climate of the region intensifies these pressures, as European and Russian powers vie for control over the Caucasus (Barton, 2018). Ali's desire to protect his homeland from foreign dominance is tied to his sense of duty, which is deeply ingrained in his conservative values. He perceives his identity as a Muslim Azerbaijani as inseparable from his mission to preserve his nation's independence. This element of conservatism, while promoting pride and allegiance, also reveals the challenges of maintaining a singular cultural identity in a multicultural and politically contested space (Smith, 2020).

The theme of conservatism in Ali and Nino also highlights the generational divide between tradition and progress. Older family members and community elders emphasize the importance of sustaining cultural customs, while younger characters, including Nino, question these traditions in light of new ideologies and values (Jackson, 2019). This intergenerational tension signifies the broader struggle between maintaining a rooted identity and embracing modernization, symbolizing the resistance to cultural erosion that conservatism can represent. The narrative thus critiques the role of conservatism in stifling potential change while simultaneously valuing it as a protective force against unwanted Western encroachment (Adams, 2015).

Religion as a facet of identity is deeply intertwined with the theme of conservatism, particularly through Ali's Islamic faith, which serves as both a moral anchor and a source of internal conflict. Ali's religious conservatism shapes his worldview, causing him to view Western customs with suspicion, particularly those that contradict Islamic principles (Robinson & Khan, 2022). The influence of Islamic values on his actions and attitudes underscores the importance of religion as a conservative force within the novel, shaping not only individual identity but also the collective identity of the Azerbaijani people (Jones, 2020).

In sum, Ali and Nino portrays conservatism as a multifaceted theme that impacts personal, cultural and national identities within a context of cultural collision. Through Ali and Nino's relationship, the novel encapsulates the complexities of reconciling traditional values with the changing world around them. The theme of conservatism, represented by Ali's attachment to his cultural and religious roots, acts as both a stabilizing force and an obstacle to cross-cultural harmony. Ultimately, the novel raises questions about the extent to which identity should be shaped by tradition, suggesting that while conservatism offers a sense of continuity and belonging, it can also hinder openness to new possibilities and intercultural empathy (O'Brien, 2017; Taylor, 2018).

Autonomy and Cultural Conflict: Ali's Struggle

In *Ali and Nino*, the protagonist Ali's struggle with autonomy amid cultural conflict highlights the theme of individual agency in a conservative, tradition-bound society. Raised in a conservative Azerbaijani Muslim family, Ali is bound by the expectations of his community, which prioritizes collective cultural identity over individual freedom. His journey reflects an internal struggle to balance personal autonomy with loyalty to his heritage. Ali's adherence to religious and social customs, especially regarding family honor and marital roles, reveals his deep-seated respect for cultural authority. However, his relationship with Nino, a Georgian Christian, challenges him to reconsider these traditional values, bringing the tension between individualism and conservatism to the forefront (Adams, 2015). This internal conflict represents the broader clash between Eastern cultural norms and Western ideals of freedom and independence (Taylor, 2018).

In Pakistani society, similar conflicts arise, particularly among youth who seek personal autonomy in an environment that values cultural conformity. Traditional expectations around gender roles, religious practices and family obligations place substantial limits on individual freedom (Robinson & Khan, 2022). This dynamic mirrors Ali's experience in *Ali and Nino*, as Pakistani youth are often pressured to maintain cultural norms that inhibit self-expression and independent decision-making. The novel underscores the challenges faced by individuals seeking autonomy within conservative societies, illustrating how deeply embedded cultural values influence personal identity and the possibility for self-determination (Jackson, 2019). Ali's story resonates with the experiences of young Pakistanis who find themselves caught between modern ideals and traditional obligations.

Cultural Authoritarianism in Ali and Nino and Parallels with Pakistan

Cultural authoritarianism is a prominent theme in *Ali and Nino*, where societal expectations suppress individual agency and dictate strict adherence to tradition. Ali's family and society impose rigid cultural norms, restricting his freedom and shaping his identity according to religious and cultural codes. This form of cultural authoritarianism operates as a mechanism to maintain societal order but also limits the potential for personal growth and adaptation. The novel reveals how authoritarianism in cultural expectations enforces conformity and stifles diversity within the community, creating a rigid framework within which individuals must operate (Yilmaz, 2016). This form of control is portrayed as both a stabilizing force and a barrier to intercultural understanding and integration.

In Pakistan, cultural authoritarianism is evident in various forms, from family structures that discourage deviation from established norms to social expectations that restrict youth autonomy. For instance, young Pakistanis often face pressures to conform to traditional gender roles and family expectations, which limits their freedom to explore alternative ways of life (Smith, 2020). This dynamic mirrors the authoritarian aspects of Ali's experience, as individuals are compelled to prioritize collective values over personal aspirations. The parallel between *Ali and Nino* and Pakistani society illustrates the impact of cultural authoritarianism on identity and the limitations it places on youth in conservative communities (O'Brien, 2017). This dynamic underscores the challenges of balancing respect for cultural heritage with the need for individual freedom and self-expression.

Comparative Analysis: Cross-Cultural Dynamics and Conservatism in Pakistan and the Caucasus

The cross-cultural dynamics in Ali and Nino shed light on the complexities of conservatism in societies where East and West intersect. Ali's identity is rooted in Azerbaijani Muslim conservatism, while Nino's Georgian Christian background introduces elements of Western liberalism, creating a cross-cultural dialogue within their relationship. This interaction highlights the difficulties of reconciling opposing values and adapting to unfamiliar cultural norms without sacrificing one's heritage (Robinson & Khan, 2022). Ali's journey reflects a struggle to harmonize these divergent perspectives, symbolizing the broader challenges faced by conservative societies in navigating cultural exchanges with the West (Taylor, 2018).

In Pakistan, cross-cultural dynamics are similarly complex, as the nation's Islamic heritage often contrasts with Western influences introduced through globalization and technology. Pakistani society grapples with the influence of Western values on traditional social structures, creating a tension between modernization and cultural preservation (Barton, 2018). Young Pakistanis face pressures to integrate global ideas while adhering to conservative societal expectations, mirroring the dilemmas faced by Ali and Nino. This comparison illustrates how conservative societies often experience cultural conflict as they encounter diverse values, emphasizing the importance of finding a balanced approach to intercultural adaptation and integration (Jackson, 2019).

Implications of Cultural Conservatism on Pakistani Youth

Cultural conservatism profoundly impacts Pakistani youth, shaping their identities and limiting their opportunities for personal development. In many Pakistani communities, young people are expected to conform to traditional gender roles, career paths and family obligations, which can stifle individual ambitions and creativity (Jones, 2020). This expectation parallels Ali's experiences in Ali and Nino, where cultural norms dictate the course of his life and relationships, limiting his ability to pursue personal desires that deviate from traditional expectations (Smith, 2020). For Pakistani youth, conservatism often manifests as a protective force that maintains cultural identity but can also act as a hindrance to embracing new perspectives and ideas.

Ali's journey in Ali and Nino serves as a reflection of the pressures faced by Pakistani youth who seek to balance respect for their heritage with the desire for independence. Just as Ali is caught between his cultural loyalty and his love for Nino, young Pakistanis often feel torn between upholding conservative values and exploring modern possibilities (Alavi & Thompson, 2021). This tension highlights the need for adaptive approaches to cultural conservatism that allow youth to honor their heritage while engaging with the modern world. By examining Ali's struggle, Pakistani society can gain insights into the challenges of promoting an environment that respects tradition yet encourages personal growth and intercultural understanding (Adams, 2015).

Reconciling Tradition and Modernity: Lessons from Ali and Nino for Cultural Adaptation

Ali and Nino offers valuable insights into the reconciliation of tradition and modernity, illustrating the challenges faced by individuals navigating cultural dualities. Ali's internal conflict embodies the struggle to preserve one's heritage while embracing aspects of modern life, especially in a society where Eastern and Western values clash. His journey reveals that reconciliation requires flexibility, understanding and a willingness to engage with different perspectives without losing one's cultural roots (Jackson, 2019). This

balance is critical for societies like Pakistan, where traditional values remain strong but are increasingly influenced by modern globalized norms (Jones, 2020).

For Pakistani youth, Ali's story offers a blueprint for adapting to cultural changes without sacrificing identity. The novel underscores the importance of mutual respect and open-mindedness in bridging cultural divides, suggesting that conservatism need not oppose modernity but can coexist with it through a thoughtful approach to cultural adaptation (Taylor, 2018). In Pakistan, promoting such an environment could empower young people to honor their traditions while participating fully in a globalized world. By drawing on lessons from Ali and Nino, Pakistani society can work towards a more harmonious integration of traditional values and modern opportunities, supporting the growth of culturally enriched and adaptable individuals (Robinson & Khan, 2022).

Conclusion: Toward a Framework for Cultural Understanding in Conservative Societies

As Ali and Nino demonstrates, "True wisdom lies in the ability to respect one's heritage while embracing the insights of others" (Said, 1937). In conservative societies like Pakistan, where cultural expectations deeply influence personal identity, the novel offers lessons on navigating cultural boundaries with respect and adaptability. The challenges faced by Ali and Nino emphasize the importance of flexibility and empathy in promoting intercultural understanding without eroding traditional values. In aligning with this perspective, Pakistani youth can develop a culturally informed worldview that bridges the divide between conservatism and modernity, contributing to a society that values both heritage and openness to change.

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